

Role of Yoga in the Psychological Factors of Human Beings

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Abstract:

The principles and practices of Yoga have been practiced form several thousand years and have been subjected for the investigation in different areas like psychology and allied sciences. They stood the test of all the time and are of great help in the achievement of best possible holistic health through their regular practice. Yoga revives our heritage and tradition and supports the modern health care system to prevent many of the modern psychosomatic diseases. In this study the researcher has made an attempt to Measure the effectiveness of yoga interventions in reducing stress levels and to systematically investigate the role of yoga in influencing psychological factors, contributing to our understanding of its potential benefits and informing the development of evidence-based interventions for enhancing mental health and well-being. The researcher has followed the descriptive method. Various secondary sources of information have been followed to gather information to fulfill the objectives of the study. Yoga is an efficient means of mental and body control, according to the research. When you're physically well, you're mentally clear, focused, and stress-free. The opportunity to spend time with loved ones and keep up positive connections with others is provided by this.

Keywords: *Yoga, Psychological Factors, Spiritual, Socially Healthy, Learned Educators.*

Introduction:

What we mean when we say "yoga" is merging our individual consciousness with the Divine Consciousness that permeates the universe in a super conscious condition called Samadhi. Physical postures (asanas) and breathing techniques (pranayamas) are the foundation of yoga, an old Eastern discipline. With the goal of merging one's physical and spiritual selves in mind, there is a cognitive component that emphasizes attention and meditation. Numerous scientific investigations have shown that yoga has a substantial effect on many facets of physical and mental health. The methods outlined in the yoga sutras had already been in use by 3000 BCE, according to archaeological evidence and other sources. According to oral tradition, the date could be much sooner. The yoga sutras have traditionally been taught verbally by experienced teachers. Experts believe that Patanjali, who flourished between 400 BCE and 200 AD, organized and collated these sutras. Patanjali lays forth the eight limbs of yoga, each of which is fundamental to the practice and integral to the total.

A healthy, happy, and prosperous life may be yours with the help of Yoga and yogic practices, which are just as applicable and beneficial in modern times for treating a wide range of mental and physical ailments. With the rise of material values, intense competition, changes in family dynamics, social mores, and community ties, and information overload brought on by the proliferation of digital media, this is more important than ever.

“People suffering with mental health problems such as depression, anxiety and stress frequently go for self-help treatments before seeking treatment from a medical or mental health professional to maximize financial savings, to refrain from consuming synthetic medications, or avoid negative stigmatization as well as in pursuance of their desire for more holistic treatment”²³. (Khalsa,.2013) “These come under complementary

²³“ Khalsa, S. S. (2013). Yoga for Psychiatry and Mental Health: An Ancient Practice with Modern Relevance. *Indian J Psychiatry*;55:334-6”.

alternative medicines which are applied to treat many sorts of mental and physical illnesses”²⁴. (Faass,.2006)

Aims of Yoga:

Yoga is the way of life; the main aim of Yoga is to prepare one for fruitful life and everlasting happiness. It's develops our physical health, mental health, social health, spiritual health and self realizations. The path of yoga is healthy mind in a healthy body. It's helps us to overcome difficulties in life through self-confidence and self determination. The main objectives of yoga are to bring balance and harmony of life. It's promoting well-being and relaxation, one of the fundamental objectives of yoga is to attain inner peace with holistic approach²⁵.

Importance of Yoga:

Yoga in itself is a science of health management rather than methods of treatment. Is played an important role to release the accumulated body problems like stiffness of joints and spasms of muscles. It helps in developing Physical fitness, good for relaxation, good for rehabilitation after injury, help to control anxiety, improve& concentration, improves immunity, regulates diet etc. Today, the whole world has realized that it is Possible to get rid of even the in curable diseases through yogasana. We can only say that if we adopt yogasana as a part of our life, no disease can even touch us. The gymnasiums only make our bodies well-built from outside whether importance of yogasana not only makes our body stout they also provide sheen to our inner strength²⁶.

Justification of the Study:

The justification of studying the role of yoga in the psychological factors of human beings lies in its potential to offer holistic well-being. Mental health issues are increasingly prevalent globally, with stress, anxiety, depression, and other psychological

²⁴“ Faass, N. (2006). Who uses complementary medicine? In D. Rakel & N. Faass (Eds.), *Complementary medicine in clinical practice* (pp. 9–17). Sudbury, MA: Jones & Bartlett”.

²⁵ “Dr. Xavier Francis G. (2011) *yoga for Health & Personality*, New-Delhi: PustakMahal”

²⁶ “Mathew Jacob (May 11, 2014) *The week health 50 yoga life-Chargers*, Kochi: Malayala Manorama Co. Ltd”.

disorders affecting individuals of all ages and backgrounds. Yoga, with its mind-body approach, has shown promise in alleviating these conditions. There is a growing body of scientific research validating the psychological benefits of yoga. Studies have shown that regular practice can reduce stress, improve mood, and enhance overall mental well-being through various mechanisms such as mindfulness, relaxation, and improved self-awareness. Yoga can serve as a complementary or alternative therapy alongside conventional treatments for psychological disorders. Its non-invasive nature and lack of significant side effects make it an attractive option for individuals seeking holistic approaches to mental health. Beyond addressing existing psychological concerns, yoga has been shown to have preventive benefits, helping individuals build resilience against stress and maintain emotional balance even in challenging situations. This preventive aspect is crucial for promoting long-term mental health. In conclusion, there is a pressing social need in the modern world for effective, easily available, and comprehensive support for mental health, and research into the function of yoga in psychological aspects may provide precisely that.

Objectives:

In this study the researcher has made an attempt to Measure the effectiveness of yoga interventions in reducing stress levels and to systematically investigate the role of yoga in influencing psychological factors, contributing to our understanding of its potential benefits and informing the development of evidence-based interventions for enhancing mental health and well-being.

Method:

In this study the researcher has followed the descriptive method. Various secondary sources of information have been followed to gather information to fulfill the objectives of the study.

Yoga and Mental Health:

According to World Health Organization (WHO, 2014), “mental health is not just the absence of mental illness. It is defined as a state of well-being in which every individual realizes his or her own potential, can cope with the normal stresses of life, can work productively and fruitfully, and is able to make a contribution to his or her community. According to Indian Philosophy, Yogas is ‘Chitta Vritti Nirodhah’-A technique to quiet the mind or the restraint of the modification of the mind-stuff is yoga”.(Patanjali, 1978/1999)²⁷ are material perks, psychological advantages, and spiritual benefits. The physical benefits of yoga include building strength, flexibility, and core stability; better posture; increased energy; improved metabolic balance; improved respiratory, digestive, endocrine, reproductive, and elimination systems; reduced blood pressure; improved lung efficiency; improved sleep; improved cardiovascular and circulatory health; pain relief; enhanced athletic performance; and improved balance. Attuning oneself to the environment, improving concentration and mental clarity, decreasing stress and anxiety, fostering positive thoughts and self-acceptance, and increasing flexibility are some of the major psychological benefits of yoga. Then there are the spiritual benefits, which include awakening one's spirit, developing a healthy spiritual awareness, promoting interdependence between mind, body, and spirit, strengthening the concept of oneness of all things, and connecting one's energy with divine energy.

Role of yoga in the psychological factors:

Yoga plays a multifaceted role in influencing the psychological factors of human beings, offering a holistic approach to mental well-being. Here's how:

1. Stress Reduction: Reduced stress levels are one of yoga's most studied advantages. Yoga helps activate the body's relaxation response via physical postures (asanas),

²⁷ “Patanjali. (1978/1999). The yoga sutras of patanjali. (Sri Swami Satchidananda, Trans.).Virginia: Integral Yoga Publications. (Original work unpublished)”.

breathing exercises (pranayama), and meditation. This, in turn, lowers levels of the stress hormone cortisol and promotes a feeling of peace and serenity²⁸.

2. Anxiety and Depression Management: Yoga has shown promise in alleviating symptoms of anxiety and depression. Regular practice can increase levels of gamma-amino butyric acid (GABA), a neurotransmitter associated with relaxation, while also enhancing mood-regulating neurotransmitters like serotonin and dopamine. Additionally, mindfulness techniques incorporated into yoga help individuals develop greater awareness of their thoughts and emotions, reducing rumination and negative thinking patterns²⁹.

3. Enhanced Emotional Regulation: Yoga cultivates emotional resilience by teaching individuals to observe and regulate their emotional responses. Through mindfulness practices, practitioners learn to acknowledge and accept their emotions without judgment, fostering greater emotional balance and equanimity in the face of life's challenges³⁰.

4. Improved Self-awareness and Self-esteem: Yoga encourages self-reflection and introspection, leading to heightened self-awareness and self-understanding. As individuals deepen their connection to their bodies, minds, and inner selves, they develop a stronger sense of self-esteem and self-compassion, fostering a positive self-image and inner confidence³¹.

5. Enhanced Cognitive Function: Research suggests that yoga can improve cognitive function, including attention, memory, and executive functioning. By promoting

²⁸ "Siddappa ,Naragatti , Management of Hypertension through Yogic practices, International journal of AYUSH 2018:7(4)19- 32".

²⁹ Smith, C., Hancock, H., Blake-Mortimer, J., & Eckert, K. (2007). A randomised comparative trial of yoga and relaxation to reduce stress and anxiety. *Complementary therapies in medicine*, 15(2), 77-83".

³⁰ "Shapiro, D., Cook, I. A., Davydov, D. M., Ottaviani, C., Leuchter, A. F., & Abrams, M. (2007). Yoga as a complementary treatment of depression: effects of traits and moods on treatment outcome. *Evidence-based complementary and alternative medicine*, 4(4), 493-502".

³¹ "Sengupta, P. (2012). Health impacts of yoga and pranayama: A state-of-the-art review. *International journal of preventive medicine*, 3(7), 444"

relaxation, reducing stress, and increasing cerebral blood flow, yoga creates an optimal environment for cognitive performance and mental clarity³².

6. Social Connection and Support: Yoga classes often provide opportunities for social interaction and community support, which are crucial for mental health. Practicing yoga in a group setting fosters a sense of belonging and connection, reducing feelings of loneliness and isolation that can contribute to psychological distress.

7. Spiritual Growth and Meaning-making: For many practitioners, yoga is not just a physical or mental practice but also a spiritual journey. Engaging in yoga can deepen one's sense of purpose and meaning in life, fostering spiritual growth and a sense of interconnectedness with oneself, others, and the universe.

Overall, yoga offers a comprehensive approach to enhancing psychological well-being, addressing various aspects of mental health such as stress, anxiety, depression, emotional regulation, self-esteem, cognitive function, social connection, and spiritual fulfillment. By integrating body, mind, and spirit, yoga empowers individuals to cultivate resilience, balance, and inner peace in their lives.

Role of yoga in the emotional well being: The role of yoga in emotional well-being is profound and multifaceted, encompassing various psychological, physiological, and spiritual dimensions. Here's a breakdown of how yoga contributes to emotional well-being³³:

- 1. Emotional Regulation:** Yoga cultivates awareness of the mind-body connection, empowering individuals to recognize and regulate their emotions more effectively. Through mindfulness practices, practitioners learn to observe their thoughts and feelings without judgment, allowing for greater emotional clarity and self-control.

³² "Saradananda Swami (2011) *amazing Yoga*, U.K., London: Hodder Education".

³³ Mathew Jacob (May 11, 2014) *The week health 50 yoga life-Chargers*, Kochi: Malayala Manorama Co. Ltd

2. **Anxiety and Depression Management:** Studies have shown that yoga can be effective in reducing symptoms of anxiety and depression. By promoting relaxation, enhancing mood-regulating neurotransmitters, and fostering a sense of inner peace, yoga offers a holistic approach to managing these common mental health conditions.
3. **Enhanced Self-awareness and Self-compassion:** Yoga encourages self-reflection and introspection, leading to greater self-awareness and self-understanding. As individuals deepen their connection to their inner selves, they develop greater self-compassion and acceptance, fostering a positive relationship with themselves and others³⁴.
4. **Release of Emotional Tension:** Physical tension often manifests as emotional tension in the body. Through the practice of yoga asanas, individuals release stored tension and emotional blockages, promoting a sense of lightness and emotional freedom.
5. **Cultivation of Gratitude and Positivity:** Yoga philosophy emphasizes the cultivation of positive qualities such as gratitude, compassion, and contentment. Through practices such as loving-kindness meditation (Metta meditation) and gratitude exercises, individuals foster a more positive outlook on life, enhancing emotional well-being.
6. **Connection to Spirituality and Inner Wisdom:** For many practitioners, yoga is not just a physical or mental practice but also a spiritual journey. By connecting with their inner selves and tapping into a sense of higher purpose or divine consciousness, individuals find solace, meaning, and fulfillment, enriching their emotional lives³⁵.
7. **Resilience-building:** Through the challenges and discomforts encountered in yoga practice, individuals develop resilience – the ability to bounce back from

³⁴“ Preksha Dhyana Human Body (part-II), Health Care-JS Zaveri, Jain Vishva Bharati, Ladnun (Raj.), edition 1993”.

³⁵“Prabhavananda, S., & Isherwood, C. Chennai: Sri Ramakrishna Math. Patanjali Yoga Sutras”.

adversity. This resilience extends beyond the yoga mat, helping individuals navigate life's ups and downs with greater ease and equanimity.

Overall, yoga offers a holistic approach to emotional well-being, addressing the interconnectedness of body, mind, and spirit. By promoting relaxation, emotional regulation, self-awareness, and spiritual growth, yoga empowers individuals to cultivate greater emotional resilience, balance, and fulfillment in their lives³⁶.

Conclusion:

Through regular yoga practice, one may gain profound mastery over one's mind, body, and spirit. Incorporating both mental and physical disciplines, it facilitates relaxation, alleviates anxiety, and promotes overall well-being. Additionally, it aids in breathing, energy, and vitality while strengthening muscles, increasing flexibility, and toning the body. Although yoga may seem like nothing more than stretching, it really has several benefits for your body, including your mood, appearance, and mobility. The widespread acceptance of Yoga in the contemporary world is evident from this fact alone. The globe has come together as a result of this incident. Yoga is a powerful tool for mastering one's thoughts and actions. When you're physically well, you're mentally clear, focused, and stress-free. The opportunity to spend time with loved ones and keep up positive connections with others is provided by this.

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³⁶ “Shankar Ganesh (1998) Holistic Approach of Yoga, Bina (M.P.): Aditya Publishers”

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